

Effect of three insecticides on green leafhopper (GLH) population and tungro (RTV) incidence

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We tested full and half of recommended rates of 3 common insecticides to control GLH: cypermethrin at 0.05 and 0.025 and monocrotophos and BPMC at 0.750 and 0.375 kg ai/ha. IR22 seedlings raised under netting to 21 d after sowing on the IRRI farm were transplanted in 5.0 × 9.8 m plots at 25- × 25- cm spacing, in 4 replications. Insecticides were sprayed 5 times at 14-d intervals from 2 to 58 d after transplanting (DT). GLH numbers were monitored (FARMCOP suction

Table 2. Effect of 3 insecticides on RTV and yield.^a IRRI, 1986.

Insecticide ^b	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Hills (%) showing RTV symptoms		Yield (t/ha)
		40 DT	65 DT	
Cypermethrin	0.05	10 a	24 a	2.9 a
	0.02	13 a	35 ab	2.8 a
Monocrotophos	0.75	16 a	36 ab	2.5 ab
	0.37	13 a	45 b	2.4 ab
BPMC	0.75	19 a	41 b	2.2 b
	0.37	17 a	46 b	2.1 b
Control		43 b	64 c	1.6 c

^aAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bInsecticides were applied at 2, 16, 30, 44, and 58 DT.

sampler machine) 1 d after each insecticide application. RTV incidence was visually estimated at 40 and 65 DT. Cypermethrin, monocrotophos, and BPMC were effective against GLH at

half of recommended rates (Table 1). Significantly fewer RTV-infected hills also were found (Table 2). Cypermethrin was superior to BPMC in controlling GLH and RTV. □

Table 1. Field evaluation of 3 insecticides to control GLH.^a IRRI, 1986.

Insecticide ^b	Rate (kg ai/ha)	GLH adults (no./10 sweeps)									
		1st spraying		2d spraying		3d spraying		4th spraying		5th spraying	
		1 DBT	1 DAT	1 DBT	1 DAT	1 DBT	1 DAT	1 DBT	1 DAT	1 DBT	1 DAT
Cypermethrin	0.05	4.8 a	1.3 a	7.8 a	1.5 a	7.0 abc	3.0 a	5.5 a	4.0 a	5.5 a	0.3 a
	0.02	4.0 a	2.5 a	10.5 ab	3.0 ab	4.5 a	6.5 ab	4.8 a	3.3 a	7.0 ab	0.0 a
Monocrotophos	0.75	6.5 a	2.8 a	7.5 a	5.8 abc	7.0 abc	6.8 ab	7.0 ab	4.8 a	11.5 bc	1.3 a
	0.37	6.5 a	2.0 a	10.3 ab	8.8 bc	10.5 bc	9.0 b	8.0 ab	5.3 a	12.0 bc	1.3 a
BPMC	0.75	6.3 a	3.8 a	6.8 a	8.0 bc	5.8 ab	9.8 b	8.0 ab	4.0 a	9.5 abc	2.8 a
	0.37	4.8 a	5.0 ab	8.0 a	10.3 cd	7.3 abc	9.0 b	9.8 ab	7.5 a	13.0 c	8.0 b
No insecticide (control)	-	6.8 a	8.5 b	14.5 b	14.8 d	11.3 c	16.3 c	12.0 b	13.0 b	13.8 c	9.8 b

^aDBT = day before treatment, DAT = day after treatment. Av of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bInsecticide applied at 2, 16, 30, 44, and 58 DT. Spray volume, 300-500 liters/ha.

Cytogenetic effects of neem seed "bitters" (NSB) on green leafhopper (GLH) males

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Exposure to neem seed derivatives has recently been found to reduce the reproductive potential of several species of insect pests. We investigated this phenomenon in *Nephotettix virescens*.

Using the lacto-aceto-orcein squash technique, we examined the meiotic cells of male progeny derived from *N. virescens* parents caged on TN1 rice

Mean frequencies of meiocytes and nonmeiocytes, and meiotic indices in progeny derived from *N. virescens* parents caged on NSB-treated TN1 rice plants.^a IRRI, 1987.

NSB treatment (ppm)	Frequency (no.)		Meiotic index
	Meiocytes	Nonmeiocytes	
0 (control)	484 a	96 b	0.83 a
100	450 a	197 a	0.69 b
500	86 b	91 b	0.48 c
2500	17 b	89 b	0.45 c

^aAv of 15 replications. 1 insect replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

plants sprayed with an aqueous solution of 100, 500, and 2,500 ppm NSB and compared them with those from control progeny.

The meiotic process, but not interphase, was significantly affected at

500 and 2,500 ppm NSB. Few spermatogonia carried on the meiotic divisions that produced primary and secondary spermatocytes. This significantly reduced the meiotic index in the progeny derived from treated